

Overcoming Data Scarcity in Human Activity Recognition*

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Abstract—Wearable sensors have become increasingly popular in recent years, with technological advances leading to cheaper, more widely available, and smaller devices. As a result, there has been a growing interest in applying machine learning techniques for Human Activity Recognition (HAR) in healthcare. These techniques can improve patient care and treatment by accurately detecting and analyzing various activities and behaviors. However, current approaches often require large amounts of labeled data, which can be difficult and time-consuming to obtain. In this study, we propose a new approach that uses synthetic sensor data generated by 3D engines and Generative Adversarial Networks to overcome this obstacle. We evaluate the synthetic data using several methods and compare them to real-world data, including classification results with baseline models. Our results show that synthetic data can improve the performance of deep neural networks, achieving a better F_1 -score for less complex activities on a known dataset by 8.4% to 73% than state-of-the-art results. However, as we showed in a self-recorded nursing activity dataset of longer duration, this effect diminishes with more complex activities. This research highlights the potential of synthetic sensor data generated from multiple sources to overcome data scarcity in HAR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) using sensors is a promising area of research in healthcare that can provide valuable insights into a patient’s health and support remote monitoring [1]. Sensors, such as Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs), are commonly used in HAR as they provide accurate and reliable data on the orientation and acceleration of a person’s body, which can be used to infer the type of activity being performed. The use of IMUs is practical in real-world settings due to their small size, lightweight nature, and ease of integration into wearable devices [2]. Additionally, the use of sensors for data collection preserves privacy compared to alternative methods, such as video or audio recordings. The benefits of HAR extend to both healthcare professionals, through more accurate and efficient documentation, and to patients, through the potential to aid in diagnosis and treatment [3].

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Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed method by synthetically generating data through GANs and a 3D engine for HAR.

The collection of ample data is critical for the effective training and testing of machine learning algorithms in the field of HAR. Data sparsity is a prevalent issue, particularly in health-related applications, as data acquisition can prove to be challenging, time-consuming, and subject to privacy concerns. This lack of data can impede the recognition of different activities. Furthermore, the scarcity of data also makes it challenging to validate and evaluate model performance, which is imperative for developing accurate and robust models. To address these challenges, data retrieval for HAR necessitates large-scale studies and the acquisition of a diverse dataset. However, the complexity of real-world factors, such as ethical concerns, participant privacy and consent, and the diversity of data sources and modalities, makes it a laborious and time-consuming task to create a dataset. This complexity limits many advancements in HAR to specific areas. Deep Learning approaches for classification require even more data with the increasing complexity of activities to be recognized [4].

Data augmentation is a common approach to increasing the amount of recorded data. There are various methods of augmentation in HAR [5]. While Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have been shown to be effective in generating new data, they require a large amount of existing data to be trained. To overcome this limitation, we propose a novel approach that leverages the power of 3D engines, such as Unity and Blender, to create animations on arbitrary activities with subsequent randomized movements of the same activity. These animations can then be used to extract virtual IMU data to train a machine learning model.

In this study, we aim to evaluate the impact of synthetic data on real-world HAR in different use cases as depicted in Figure 1. To do this, we will use various methods to evaluate the generated data based on its similarity with real data and

its influence on classification performance. Our original data source consists of a subset of the PAMAP2 [6] dataset and one self-recorded dataset containing nursing activities [7]. We believe that by using GANs and 3D engines, we can significantly improve the model performance and make a meaningful impact in the field of HAR, especially in the healthcare context.

The work proceeds as follows: We will discuss related work in the field of synthetic data generation for HAR in section II. In section III, we will describe our implementation and methodology for generating synthetic data using GANs and Unity as a 3D engine. Results and evaluation of the performance of our synthetic data on real-world HAR tasks will be presented in section IV. Section section V will be dedicated to the discussion and conclusion of our work, where we will discuss the implications of our results and the potential impact of synthetic data generation on the field of HAR and suggest potential avenues for future research in this area.

II. RELATED WORK

In recent years, various data augmentation methods have been proposed to address the problem of data sparsity in HAR [1]. So far, GANs and 3D engines have been used separately as data augmentation techniques for HAR.

For example, Chen et al. showed that increasing the amount of training data using GANs can improve performance on a public dataset of low-level human activities [8]. Alharbi et al. showed that oversampling unbalanced data using GANs leads to significant F_1 score improvements on two different human activity datasets [9]. Hoelzmann et al. proposed a method to counteract overfitting using GAN-based data augmentation techniques and applied it to the PAMAP2 dataset, achieving an F_1 -score improvement of 11% and 5% for subject-wise and fold-wise augmentation, respectively [10]. However, subject-wise augmentation expands the dataset for each subject, which may lead to biased evaluation results. Our proposed method aims to construct a pipeline that resembles a real-world scenario, using only training data for the entire augmentation process.

Previous research has investigated the use of 3D animation engines to create realistic representations of human body motions. A study by Kang et al. proposed a data collection framework using virtual reality applications and simulation tools to capture avatar activities and generate virtual IMU data for training machine learning models [11]. While this approach can be effective for generating virtual IMU data from animations, it has limitations regarding the amount of data generated. In addition, the method is limited to using pre-existing animations, which are often restricted to specific, simple motions. As such, this approach may be inadequate for generating a comprehensive dataset for more complex activities, particularly those encountered in healthcare contexts.

Our research differs from previous studies in several ways. While previous studies have primarily focused on using pre-existing, simple animations, we have developed a method

for generating animations of any activity, including those that are complex in nature. In addition, we also use an augmentation method for animations to enhance our dataset further. Furthermore, we investigate the impact of using a combination of GANs and 3D engines for data generation. We conducted experiments on the PAMAP2 dataset [6] and one novel dataset on nursing activities [7] to evaluate the proposed methods. We also present a pipeline for comparing and analyzing different data augmentation techniques and investigate the effect of combining data augmentation with transfer learning on model performance.

III. OVERCOMING DATA SCARCITY

In this section, we present the datasets, the data generation pipeline, the analysis, and the evaluation methods used to assess the effectiveness of our proposed augmentation strategies.

A. Datasets

We selected two datasets for our experiments: PAMAP2 [6], a widely used dataset in the field of HAR; and SONAR-LAB, a dataset on nursing activities [7].

1) *PAMAP2*: The PAMAP2 dataset is a publicly available benchmark that contains 18 daily activities recorded from nine participants equipped with three IMUs and a heart rate monitor. The IMUs were placed on the chest, wrist, and ankle of the dominant side of the participants' bodies and collected data at a frequency of 100 Hz. Each IMU had 3-axis sensors for acceleration, gyroscope, and magnetic field, and a 1-axis sensor for heart rate and temperature data, yielding an 11-dimensional input space. For the purpose of this study, only the wrist sensor and six activities (lying, sitting, standing, walking, ironing, and vacuuming) performed for the same length of time by eight subjects were used.

2) *SONAR-LAB*: The SONAR-LAB dataset is a collection of 14 nursing activities performed in a laboratory setting and recorded over three weeks from ten male subjects aged 21-42 years, including one professional nurse, while the others were primarily research institute staff. Three individuals collected the data: a nurse, a patient, and a labeler. Four cameras were used to capture the sessions, which were then used to re-label the data and enhance label accuracy. The nurse wore five Xsens™ DOT sensors placed at five different body locations (two wrists, two ankles, and one waist), transmitting sensor data to a smartphone via Bluetooth. Each IMU had 3-axis sensors for acceleration and magnetic field and 4-axis sensors for orientation, resulting in a 50-dimensional input space from the five sensors. Data was collected at a frequency of 60 Hz and had a recording time of approximately 8 hours. The entire dataset was used for the study, excluding the *null activity* label, which represents activities not represented by the available labels during data recording.

B. Synthetic Data Generation

In our study, we evaluated two distinct data generation strategies. To this end, we developed separate pipelines for the two strategies. Each pipeline was designed to generate

synthetic sensor data for every activity in the datasets. The first approach involved the use of GANs to generate synthetic sensor data, while the second approach incorporated the use of a 3D engine to create animations and subsequently augment the animations to generate more diverse synthetic sensor data. In the following, both approaches are described in further detail.

1) *Synthetic Data through GANs*: For the purpose of our task we used TimeGAN [12]. TimeGAN is a GAN designed for generating sequential data, such as time series data. It uses a combination of Recurrent Neural Networks and GANs to learn the underlying patterns and distributions of the data. The generator network generates new sequences, while the discriminator network attempts to distinguish the generated sequences from the real ones. Over time, the two networks improve their abilities and the generator is able to produce more realistic and diverse sequences.

In a contemporary setting, we devised a pipeline for data generation using GANs. This pipeline consists of several stages, which are executed in a sequential manner. The initial stage involves loading and preprocessing the data by eliminating missing values. This is followed by applying feature-wise forward-fill, which is faster to execute than linear interpolation, and there was no significant difference in performance between the two methods as determined by our experiments. Additionally, we refrained from normalizing the data during preprocessing to retain the authenticity of the raw sensor data.

Subsequently, after the preprocessing stage, the data is divided into training and validation sets through the application of Leave-One-Subject-Out Cross-Validation (LOSO-CV). This process entails removing one subject from the training data and training the GAN network on the remaining subjects' data, with the left-out subject serving as the validation set. The LOSO-fold utilized for training was then partitioned into overlapping windows, and each window was further categorized into groups of similar activities. A separate GAN was trained for each distinct activity group.

The PAMAP2 dataset was analyzed using a sliding window approach, with a window size of 1 second and a step size of 1 second applied to segment the input data. The class of each window was determined by the label of the final time step within the interval, resulting in non-overlapping windows of shape (100, 11). Conversely, for the SONAR-LAB dataset, a jumping window approach, known as non-overlapping sliding windows, was employed, in which windows of 5 seconds in length were used. The step size in this approach was adjusted to skip windows that lacked a single activity, and the label for each segment corresponded to the activity performed during the interval. However, this resulted in the need to discard activities with durations of less than 5 seconds to minimize the number of transitional gestures between activity changes. The window lengths used in this research were determined to be the best performing through a comprehensive grid search process. The number of segments generated per dataset after windowing is summarized in Table I. For each activity, we synthesized ten times the

number of initial windows.

Dataset	PAMAP2	SONAR-LAB
Segmentation strategy	Sliding	Jumping
Number of windows	10,788	4,500
Window shape (time steps, features)	(100, 11)	(300, 50)
Window size in seconds	1	5
Lost recording time	0	20 minutes

TABLE I: Overview of PAMAP2 SONAR-LAB after windowing.

We utilized the Keras¹ library within TensorFlow for our implementation. The experiments were conducted with a batch size of 128, and the number of epochs was 20.

2) *Synthetic Data through Animations*: In the approach for generating synthetic data through the creation of animations, a 3D engine such as Unity² was employed. The utilization of Mixamo³, a web-based service for creating and animating 3D characters, as already proposed in [11], was a key component of this method. Mixamo offers a library of pre-made characters and animations that can be customized and used in various projects. However, in cases where a specific animation was unavailable on Mixamo due to its complexity, especially in a healthcare context, a novel approach was taken. RADiCAL⁴, which utilizes Artificial Intelligence technology to create 3D animations, was employed. The software allows for the automatic creation of animations from 2D images and the ability to fine-tune them using machine learning algorithms, offering a new way to address the issue of unavailable animations on Mixamo.

Once the animations were acquired, we advanced them using a variety of techniques. One method involved the implementation of GANimator, a generative model that has the ability to synthesize unique motions from a single, brief motion sequence, as described in [13]. This method created new motions by learning from existing ones, generating motions that closely resemble the core elements of the original motion while at the same time producing novel and diverse movements. As another approach for generating multiple animations from one, we employed Unity's Xorshift 128 algorithm to randomly modify specific parameters of the animation, referred to as Xor128. The algorithm generated random values for certain parameters, such as speed or direction, which were then applied to the animation. This process enabled the creation of numerous variations of the original animation without requiring manual creation. For instance, we could use the algorithm to randomly change the walking speed of a character or the rotation angle of a limb, resulting in a vast array of new animations from a single original animation. Finally, as a third method, we used Unity's Mecanim mechanism to randomly select and blend different animations. The resulting data generated from this process is referred to as MecanimU. The aggregated

¹<https://keras.io/>

²<https://unity.com/>

³<https://www.mixamo.com/>

⁴<https://radicalmotion.com/>

duration of the generated animations for the two datasets was computed as follows: For PAMAP2, base animations were 9.6 minutes, augmented animations through Unity’s built-in functions were 192 minutes, and animations synthesized by GANimator were 30 minutes. For SONAR-LAB, base animations were 40 minutes, augmented animations through Unity’s built-in functions were 600 minutes, and animations synthesized by GANimator were 50 minutes.

After animation creation and extension, we placed virtual sensors, matching real-world sensor placement, on the skin surface of the animation object. Through these virtual sensors, we were able to retrieve positional and orientational data, which were then converted into acceleration and angular velocity, resulting in virtual IMU data. An overview of the pipeline is depicted in Figure 2.

For the different datasets, we used a fixed timestamp to match the real-data frequency of 0.0167 (60 Hz) for SONAR-LAB and 0.01 (100 Hz) for PAMAP2. For retrieving basic animations in PAMAP2, Mixamo was used for standing, sitting, lying, and walking. However, for animations with more complex activities, such as ironing and vacuuming, we recorded a video of the activity and used RADiCAL. We did the same to create animations for SONAR-LAB, as the activities were too specific.

C. Synthetic Data Analysis

In order to draw meaningful conclusions from our later experiments, it is crucial to gain an understanding of the characteristics and similarity of the generated data in comparison to real data. To achieve this, we employed a two-pronged approach: First, we visualized the distribution of each activity through the use of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) to examine the resemblance of the synthetic data to the original distributions. Secondly, to provide a statistical analysis of the similarity of the distributions, we utilized the Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) as a sample-based metric. The MMD is a measure of the difference between two probability distributions, it’s a non-parametric method that compares the means of two sets of data in a reproducing kernel Hilbert space, and it’s often used to compare real and synthetic data. A small MMD value indicates that the two probability distributions being compared are more similar, while a large MMD value indicates that the distributions are dissimilar.

D. Synthetic Data Evaluation

The evaluation protocol adopted in this study comprises of two distinct components: the analysis results and the model results. The former leverages visual and statistical techniques to assess the similarity between the synthetic data distribution and the real data. The latter involves three comparative assessments, each examining a different method of utilizing synthetic data in the training process. The first comparison involves the Train on Synthetic, Test on Real (TSTR) method, where the data is trained on synthetic data and evaluated on real data, following the approach outlined in [14] and detailed in algorithm 1. The second comparison

involves blending the entire dataset and evaluating the results on the real dataset alone, referred to as *Mix*. The third comparison explores the application of transfer learning, where the model is trained on synthetic data, followed by retraining on a subset of real data with frozen layers to retain the learned characteristics. This retraining step is referred to as the *Transfer* evaluation. An optional finetuning step follows, which entails unfreezing all layers and fine-tuning the model with a decreased learning rate. The final evaluation, referred to as the *Transfer + Finetuning* evaluation, is conducted after this step. This study investigates the impact of freezing the first and first two convolutional layers during finetuning, and the effects of reducing the learning rate from $1e-3$ to $1e-5$.

Algorithm 1: Train on Synthetic, Test on Real (TSTR)

```

1 train, test = test.train.split(data)
2 generator = get.synthetic.data.generator()
3 with labels from train:
4     synthetic = generator.generate.synthetic(labels)
5     classifier = train.classifier(synthetic, labels)
6 with labels and test_data from test:
7     predictions = classifier.predict(test_data)
8     TSTR_score = evaluate(predictions, labels)

```

The training methodology involves the use of a Convolutional Neural Network-Long Short-Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) architecture. The model architecture, denoted as C(32)-C(64)-R(128)-R(128)-Sm, where C represents convolutional layers, R represents LSTM layers, and Sm represents a softmax layer, was selected based on its competitive performance compared to other state-of-the-art models such as DeepConvLSTM [15] and ResNet [16]. The Adam optimizer with default parameters was employed, with a default learning rate of $1e-3$.

We evaluated the impact of each synthetic dataset on TSTR, mix, and transfer learning in various settings. A LOSO evaluation method was employed for all approaches. Feature-wise forward-fill was applied to eliminate missing values in the data, and all data were normalized feature-wise to a standard distribution prior to training or inference. The synthetic GAN data follows the same distribution as the real data; thus, the same scaling as for the real data was applied. However, the animation-sourced datasets from GANimator and MecanIMU have a different value distribution than the real data; thus, a standard scaler trained only on the animation-sourced data was applied to match the value distribution of the real data. Additionally, it should be noted that raw data from Unity data exhibits a high degree of noise, which may impact the model’s performance.

IV. RESULTS

The results section presents the analysis’s outcome and the model’s performance.

A. Analysis Results

We present the results of the analysis on two datasets. We examined PCA and t-SNE visualizations for a random

Fig. 2: Unity generation pipeline. Animation data is collected in two different ways, then Blender is used to make sure they are correct. Afterward, the whole data is used in either GANimator or for augmentation inside Unity. Either way the animations will be loaded into Unity. In the end their playspeed will be modified and they will be used to generate synthetic IMU data.

selection of activities in each dataset, along with MMD scores. Figure 3 illustrates the visualization results for the *standing* activity of the PAMAP2 dataset. Our results through PCA and t-SNE indicate that the data generated by the MecanIMU approach shows the highest level of overlap with the original data.

The results of MMD scores for the PAMAP2 and SONAR-LAB datasets are shown in Table II. The table compares the performance of the four different augmentation methods: TimeGAN, GANimator, MecanIMU, and Xor128.

For the PAMAP2 dataset, the lowest average MMD score was achieved by MecanIMU, followed by TimeGAN. In particular, some activities such as lying, sitting, and standing achieved very low MMD scores, indicating high similarity between the generated and original data distributions for these activities. On the other hand, more dynamic activities such as walking and vacuum cleaning had higher MMD scores, suggesting lower similarity.

The SONAR-LAB dataset showed a similar pattern, with MecanIMU achieving the lowest average MMD score, followed by TimeGAN. For this dataset, some activities such as clean, make bed, and skin care achieved low MMD scores, indicating high similarity between the generated and original data. However, activities such as serve food and prepare medicine had higher MMD scores, suggesting lower similarity.

In conclusion, the results highlight the potential of using augmentation methods to increase the size and diversity of the training data, as well as to overcome the limitations of traditional methods. MecanIMU showed the best performance overall, achieving the lowest average MMD score for both datasets. These results contribute to the field of HAR and could be applied in various domains, including healthcare and assistive technology.

PAMAP2				
Activity	A	B	C	D
Lying	0.080	0.254	0.088	0.812
Sitting	0.164	0.100	0.049	0.734
Standing	0.057	0.079	0.059	0.862
Walking	0.009	0.135	0.008	0.951
Vacuum cleaning	0.109	0.014	0.014	0.888
Ironing	0.087	0.050	0.021	0.902
Average score	0.084	0.105	0.039	0.858
SONAR-LAB				
Clean	0.258	0.051	0.040	0.970
Make bed	0.010	0.099	0.005	0.970
Documentation	0.059	0.257	0.119	1.22
Cleaning routine in bed	0.055	0.181	0.005	0.976
Pour drinks	0.283	0.427	0.344	1.378
Comb hair	0.296	0.174	0.066	1.027
Push wheelchair	0.130	0.149	0.019	0.975
Wheelchair transfer	0.205	0.074	0.017	0.972
Dress	0.420	0.106	0.004	0.984
Serve food	0.025	0.148	0.126	1.181
Prepare medicine	0.048	0.281	0.192	1.201
Wipe dust	0.204	0.085	0.024	1.007
Skin care	0.061	0.043	0.012	0.975
Average score	0.158	0.159	0.074	1.064

TABLE II: Summary of MMD scores for all activities in each dataset. Four augmentation methods are compared: (A) TimeGAN, (B) GANimator, (C) MecanIMU, (D) Xor128. The lower the score, the closer the generated distribution is to the original one. For PAMAP2, the table only includes data for LOSO-fold without subject 3.

Overall, our results suggest a correlation between MMD scores and the degree of visual overlap between real and generated distributions across the datasets.

B. Model Results

The analysis of synthetic data revealed that mixing synthetic data with real data improves the accuracy of the model. As shown in Table III, training on only synthetic data sourced

Fig. 3: PCA (1st row) and t-SNE (2nd row) visualizations for *standing* in PAMAP2. The distributions contain data from the LOSO-fold. Each column provides visualizations for each of the four compared benchmarks. Red denotes original data, blue denotes synthetic.

from Unity animations resulted in a performance of 20% or below, however, adding real data to the training set resulted in a drastic improvement, even surpassing the performance of GAN data mixed with real data.

Data Configuration	TSTR	Mix
Real (Baseline)	0.646	
GAN	0.621	0.670
MecanIMU	0.127	0.691
GANimator	0.193	0.730
All Synthetic Data	0.614	0.704

TABLE III: Average F_1 -Scores of all mixed and synthetic configurations on the PAMAP2 dataset over all LOSO-folds.

Further analysis of all k-fold runs revealed that the synthetic data not only improves the performance, it also reduces the standard deviation in model performance. The transfer learning approach on the PAMAP2 dataset yielded varying results, as shown in Table IV. The GAN data did not benefit from the approach and showed lower performance than the model trained on only real data. The animation-sourced data through GANimator improved performance, particularly when freezing two layers. Finetuning brought a slight improvement when freezing one layer, but only an increase for the MecanIMU data when freezing two layers.

Data Configuration (Source dataset)	1 Layer frozen		2 Layer frozen	
	Transfer	Transfer + Finet.	Transfer	Transfer + Finet.
Real (Baseline)	0.646			
GAN	0.616	0.632	0.620	0.616
MecanIMU	0.639	0.645	0.659	0.668
GANimator	0.667	0.679	0.680	0.679
All Synthetic Data	0.661	0.662	0.649	0.643

TABLE IV: Average F_1 -Scores of transfer learning from synthetic data to the PAMAP2 dataset over all LOSO-folds.

As shown in Table V, the results of mixing synthetic data with real data on the SONAR-LAB dataset did not significantly improve performance. The best case, using real and GAN data, only maintains the performance level. However, in all other cases, the performance drops. All configurations trained on only synthetic data generate low performance results. Compared to the PAMAP2 mixing results, training with GANimator and real data increased its lead over the MecanIMU animation data. The MecanIMU mixed with real data performs around 4 percentage points worse than the real model, while the model trained on GANimator-sourced data and real data is only 3 percentage points worse.

Data Configuration	TSTR	Mix
Real (Baseline)	0.574	
GAN	0.333	0.578
MecanIMU	0.114	0.535
GANimator	0.104	0.542
All Synthetic Data	0.282	0.563

TABLE V: Average F_1 -Scores of all mixed and synthetic configurations on the SONAR-LAB dataset.

Similar results can be found with the transfer learning approach, as shown in Table VI.

Data Configuration (Source dataset)	1 Layer frozen		2 Layer frozen	
	Transfer	Transfer + Finet.	Transfer	Transfer + Finet.
Real (Baseline)	0.574			
GAN	0.530	0.489	0.549	0.535
MecanIMU	0.488	0.502	0.429	0.435
GANimator	0.482	0.51	0.471	0.46
All Synthetic Data	0.461	0.511	0.526	0.521

TABLE VI: Average F_1 -Scores of transfer learning from synthetic data to the SONAR-LAB dataset over all LOSO-folds.

Fig. 4: Comparison of runs with different adaptation set sizes, given as fraction of real data used. The model was trained on a fraction of the available SONAR-LAB data.

1) *Impact of Data Scale on Model Performance:* In our experiments, we also sought to evaluate the impact of the size of the dataset on the performance of our models. To this end, we conducted evaluations on the SONAR-LAB dataset by using different portions of real data while keeping the entire synthetic dataset constant. The synthetic data was mixed with the real data for training purposes. The results, illustrated in Figure 4, are extremely encouraging and highlight the benefits of incorporating synthetic data in training models.

The line plot depicts that models trained with a combination of real and synthetic data consistently exhibit better performance compared to models trained using only a subset of real data. This indicates that even when limited amounts of real data are available, the use of synthetic data can still lead to improved results. These findings are a major step forward for the field and offer new opportunities for effectively training models with limited real data.

V. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

This research aimed to evaluate the potential of synthetic data in enhancing HAR performance. The study leveraged GANs and 3D engines by synthesizing animation-based data to augment the dataset. Our findings demonstrate that the use of synthetic data has the capacity to improve classification accuracy, as evidenced by the substantial improvements observed in the PAMAP2 dataset.

However, it should be noted that the results were not universal, as the performance varied with the type and dynamics of activities, with simpler and repetitive movements exhibiting easier classification compared to more complex, diverse, and extended activities. This variation is attributed to the complex data distribution of the latter, which is challenging to replicate with synthetic data generation. As a result, the synthetic data may not accurately depict the real-world variations of these activities, leading to suboptimal model performance.

In conclusion, the potential of synthetic data to improve HAR performance is substantial, and further research is necessary to comprehend its impact on different datasets and activities. To address these limitations, future studies could focus on enhancing the realism of synthetic data generation by incorporating multi-sensor data, context information, and more diverse animations. Additionally, alternative approaches to synthetic data generation that better capture the complex distributions of real-world activities should also be explored. Further research in this area holds great promise for breakthroughs.

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